

Effects of Inquiry – Based Instructional Strategy on Achievement and Retention in Auto-Mechanics among Technical College Students in Lagos State, Nigeria

Owoso J.O.¹

Owosoluropo@gmail.com

08033069538

Olayinka Olufemi¹

olayinkaolufemi@gmail.com

08034914266

Njoku C.A.²

Njokuchiso@gmail.com

+1639384076

¹College of Information and Technology Education, Lagos State University of Education, Oto/Ijanikin, Lagos State, Nigeria

² Reliability Maintenance Unit, Amazon Fulfillment Center, Canada

Abstract

This study was designed to determine the effects of the inquiry- based instructional strategy on the achievement and retention of auto- mechanics students in technical colleges, a pre-test, post-test, non-equivalent control group, quasi- experimental design was adopted.. The population of the study consisted all the students in Tech 11 in all the technical colleges in Lagos State during the 2022/2023 academic session. A sample size of 340 students were selected from the population using multi stage random sampling technique Two research questions and two null hypotheses, tested at 0.05 level of significance, guided the study. The instruments used for data collection were cognitive achievement test (CAT) and two lesson plans (constructivist and conventional). The items of the CAT were drawn based on table of specifications built in order to ensure its content validity .and reliability coefficient of 0.80.was obtained using Pearson product moment correlational coefficient Mean and standard deviation statistics were used to answer the research questions while ANCOVA was employed to test the hypotheses at 0.05 level of significance. The study revealed that students taught auto-mechanics using the inquiry -based instructional strategy had a higher mean score than students taught using the conventional teaching method.in achievement test and test for retention .of learning The researcher recommended that, the National Board for Technical Education (NBTE) should consider a review of motor vehicle mechanics work curriculum for technical colleges with a view of incorporating the inquiry –based instructional strategy into the teaching of auto-mechanics in the technical colleges.

Keywords: Inquiry-based learning, auto-mechanics, technical college, achievement, retention and constructivism

Introduction

Auto-mechanics technology involves the application of scientific knowledge in the design, selection of materials, construction, operation and maintenance of automobile vehicles. Auto-mechanics is one of the mechanical trades (Federal Republic of Nigeria (FRN), 2004) offered as motor vehicle mechanics work in Nigeria technical colleges. The programme for motor vehicle mechanics work in Nigeria technical colleges is designed to produce competent craftsmen. According to National Board for Technical Education (NBTE, 2001) a craftsman in motor vehicle mechanics work is expected to test, diagnose, service and completely repair any fault relating to the automobile vehicle main units and systems to the manufacturers' specification.

A national curriculum is adopted in all the technical colleges accredited by NBTE. The programmes in technical colleges are offered at two levels leading to the award of National Technical Certificate (NTC) and Advanced National Technical Certificate (ANTC) for craftsmen and master craftsmen respectively (FME, 2000).

Technology the world over is dynamic. With advancement in technology petrol engine automobiles that are adopted or assembled in automobile industries nowadays are coming with new devices. For instance, (Nice ,2001) pointed out that automobiles manufactured in the United States of America with carburetor was in 2001. Nowadays, the petrol engines automobiles employ electronic injection system. Thus, technological development in automobiles has rendered traditional skills inadequate. Obviously automobile industries are in need of craftsmen who can adapt to the changes in technology in the

industries. The challenges, for preparing students for the 21st century, workplace basic skills therefore has necessitated a shift from instructional approaches based on behavioural learning theories learning theories to those rooted in cognitive psychological learning theories for which constructivism instructional techniques is one (Ogwo & Oranu,2006). Constructivism according to (Epstein & Ryan,2012) is based on the concept that learning is a constructive process in which the learner is building an internal illustration of knowledge on a personal interpretation of experience. Constructivism is a theory of learning based on the ideas that knowledge is constructed by the learner based on mental activity.

Constructivism, according to (Owoso,2016) is therefore, a model of instruction and learning and interactive process in social setting; it is problem solving oriented, allow students to explore and work in groups, making meaning of task and setting out to solving problems that are perplexing to them. Robin (2010) pointed out that the goals of instruction in a constructivist classroom are to help learners develop learning and thinking strategies, focus on individuals' active construction of knowledge, and facilitate learning by encouraging active inquiry. Robin explained that a constructivist teacher should guide learners to question tacit assumptions and help students to uncover meanings which encourage students to become self-regulatory, self-mediating and self-aware (acquisition of thinking skill). Teacher also takes on the role of a coach or guide and engaging students in active dialogue. Besides, teacher using constructivist approach would also provide students-centered instruction in complex learning environments with formats appropriate to the learner's current state of understanding that incorporate activities (authentic task), provide for social negotiation (Oral discourse), provide students with the opportunity to work collaboratively which develop in the students' ability to work cooperative learning).

The obvious implications of the use of constructivist instructional techniques such as collaborative work. Oral discusses, authentic learning and framing presented is to improve student thinking skills and problem solving abilities. The world of work nowadays is characterized by new management systems, production process, and global competitiveness, employers are demanding their workers to have cognitive skills in critical thinking, problem solving, as high-level technical and basic academic skills. Perhaps, if these are adopted in technical colleges, it will assist in developing students' thinking skills and problem solving abilities which in turn will enhance their cognitive achievement and retention of learning Constructivist instructional approach is defined in this study, as an eclectic approach to teaching which involved the use of thinking skills, oral discourse, authentic/ situated learning, collaborative work and framing instructional strategies combined during the lesson as appropriate to suit the content of the lesson in such a way that made the students construct their own knowledge and accomplish their learning tasks based on Jerome Brunner's three principles that guide development of instruction in a constructivist classroom listed in (UNESCO, 2012). These are: instruction must be concerned with experiences and contexts that make students willing and able to learn (readiness); instruction must be structured so that the students can easily grasp it (spiral organization) and instruction should be designed to facilitate extrapolation and/or fill in the gap (going beyond information given).

The present methods of teaching auto-mechanics in the technical colleges are based on the behavioural learning theories. These present methods include demonstration and lecture methods (Oranu, 2013). Oranu maintained that these methods which are based on behavioural learning theories are teacher-centred and do not give students enough opportunities to participate in the classroom instructions. The shortcoming in these methods of teaching which is due to absence of students' active involvement in classroom activities during instruction could be responsible for poor performance of Technical College students in engineering trades which include motor vehicle mechanic work in public examinations. According to (Federal ministry of education, 2015; Aina, 2017) a close examination of the factors responsible for the high failure rate among others includes poor quality of teaching in the technical colleges. Moreover, the preparation of workers for entry-level jobs and advancement in the workplace requires educational programs that provide not only job skills, but also higher-order thin king, problem solving, and collaborative work skills, but also higher-order thinking, problem solving, and collaborative work skills.(Doolittle & Camp (2010) These methods employed by teachers in the technical college thus, seen inadequate for equipping the students studying auto-mechanics with the work place basic skills required for work in the auto-mechanics with the work place basic skills required for work in the automobile industries which is vast changing with technological advancements. The raises the questions as to whether beside the teacher-centred method there is no such teachings technique of the constructivist instructional approach which can influence this ugly trend in the subject. Inquiry –based instructional strategy employed in this study is structured on the principles of constructivism.

Perhaps if inquiry-based instructional techniques are adapted in the teaching of auto-mechanics technology students in the technical colleges will be able to acquires workplace basic skills such as collaborative work skills, problem solving skills and thinking skills required in the vast technological world of work and be able to transfer learning other varying technological conditions. Hence, what will be the effects of inquiry –based instructional strategy on the achievement and retention of auto-mechanics students in the technical colleges?

Objective of the study

The objective of the study is to determine the effects of the inquiry -based instructional strategy on the cognitive achievement and retention of learning of auto-mechanics students in technical colleges in lagos state. Specifically, the objective of the study is to:

1. Determine the achievement scores of students taught auto-mechanics with inquiry –based instructional strategy and those taught using the conventional lecture and demonstration teaching methods.
2. Compare the scores of students taught auto-mechanics with inquiry –based instructional strategy and those taught using the conventional lecture and demonstration teaching methods.in the test of retention of learning.

Research questions

The following research questions were formulated to guide this study:

1. What are the mean achievement scores of students taught auto-mechanics using the inquiry- based instructional strategy and those taught using the conventional lecture and demonstration teaching methods in lagos state technical colleges?
2. What are the mean scores of students taught auto-mechanics using the inquiry-based instructional strategy and those taught using the conventional teaching methods in the test for retention of learning in lagos state technical colleges?

Hypotheses

The following null hypotheses tested at .05 level of significance guided the study:

1. **H₀₁**: There is no significant difference between the mean achievement scores of students taught auto-mechanics using inquiry-based instructional strategy and those taught using the conventional lecture and demonstration teaching methods in lagos state technical colleges.
2. **H₀₂**There is no significant difference between the mean retention scores of students taught auto-mechanics with inquiry-based instructional approach and those taught using the conventional lecture and demonstration teaching methods in lagos state technical colleges.

Theoretical framework

Theory is the foundation of any research. According to (Olaitan, Ali, Eyo & Sowande, 2010) theory is a postulation requiring further explanation in order to make meaning. The following are the theories on which this study is based. The Cognitive Theory of learning and The Constructivist Theory of Teaching and Learning.

Cognitive learning theory

Learning involves the process of storing, transformation and retrieving information. The problem of understanding how humans learn is essentially the problem of understanding how information is stored information is retrieved for use in the further learning and problem solving (Steward & Aiken, 2012). The knowledge structures are stored in semantic memory as schema or cognitive maps (UNESCO, 2012;. Shell ,2013) noted that the main emphasis of cognitive theory is on sequence of learning materials and experiences in a well-organized environment so as to create order, meaningfulness and understanding, that is, learner-environment interacting meaningfully some of the proponents of the cognitive theory and discussed below:

(Aushel, 2015) in his theory known as ‘sub-sumption model’ advocated for ‘meaningful’ as opposed to ‘rote learning’ According to him, meaningful learning occurs when there is an interaction between the students’ appropriate element in knowledge that already exist and the new materials to be learnt. However, where interaction does not take place, rote learning occurs. Those parts of the learner’s cognitive structure (organization of knowledge) which can provide for the interaction necessary for meaningful learning are called “subsumers”. A subsume is a principle or a generalized body of knowledge that the learner already acquired that can provide for association or ‘anchorage for the various components of the new knowledge, while sub-sumption model is an instructional device in which central and highly unifying ideas are stated in terms already familiar to the learner, to which he can meaningfully relate new learning materials by subsumption.

The developmental psychology of Jean Piaget recognizes the active role of both learner and his environment in the learning process. Piaget asserts that the basis of all learning is the learner’s activity as he interacts with his physical and social environment. for learning to take place, the environment must be stimulating and encouraging learning (Nwachukwu, 2010). Based on his research on the development of learner’s cognitive functions, Piaget observed that learning occurs through adaptation to interactions with the environment. Disequilibrium (mental conflict which demands resolution) gives rise to Assimilation of a new experience, which is added to the existing knowledge of the learner, or to Accommodation, which is modification of existing mental structure of the learner, then the information is very different from the existing mental structure (i.e Accommodation) (Ngwoke & Eze, 2014). The learner has an active role in constructing his or her own knowledge in both of these ideas. According to UNESCO (2012) Piaget was of the notion that as children assimilated new information into their

existing mental structures, their ideas gained complexity and power and their understanding of the world grew in richness and depth. These ideas are core concepts of the constructivism view of the learning process.

Bruner in his own theory emphasized that learning is an active process in which learner construct new ideas or concepts based upon their prior knowledge and experience (Nwachukwu, 2018). According to UNESCO (2002) Bruner identified three principles that guide the development of instruction. These include: (1) Instruction must be concerned with the experiences and contexts that make the student willing and able to learn readiness); (2) Instruction must be structured so that the student can easily grasp it (spiral organization) and, (3) Instruction should be designed to facilitate extrapolation and /or fill in the gaps (going beyond the information giving). Conclusively, the theories discussed so far believe in the environmental influences on the learner's achievement in learning and that meaningful learning occur as learner and his environment are always participating in a simultaneous mutual interaction. In this study, constructivist learning strategies –oral discourse, authentic learning, and collaborative work skill, thinking skill and learning frames emphasized students-centered learning environment. It provides a rich collaborative environment enabling the learner to consider diverse and multiple perspectives to address issues and solve problems. It also provides opportunities for the student to reflect on his or her learning in the process of learning in the classroom.

The constructivist theory of teaching and learning

Mendor (2012) in his own point of view sees constructivism as a teaching approach, which holds the views that scientific knowledge is personally constructed and reconstructed by the learner based on his prior knowledge or experience. In this context Grey (2015) defined constructivism by reference to four principles; learning in an important way, depends on what we already know; new ideas occur as we adapt and change our old ideas; learning involves inventing ideas rather than mechanically accumulating facts; meaningful learning occurs through rethinking old ideas and coming to new conclusions about new ideas which conflict with our old ideas

According to (Kozloff ,2010) a constructivist framework challenges teachers to create environments in which the teacher and student are encouraged to think and explore. Kozloff centered approach to teaching and learning: from this perspective constructivist classroom then, consist of learner centered, active instruction. In such a classroom, the teacher provides students with experiences that allow them to hypothesize, predict and manipulate object, poses questions, research investigate, imagine, and invent (Grey, 2015).

Many science educators recommend the application of constructivism to teaching. (Clemiso,, 2012;: Roth, 2010; Cheung & Taylor 2015; Vosniadou, 2010; Nworgu, 2014). Constructivist theory argues that learners bring to the classroom ideas that affect new information received. (Stofflet, 2010). What a student learn results from the interaction between what is brought to the learning situation and what is experienced and this brings a conflict instead of understanding and acquisition of science process skills. (Stofflet (2010), stressed the fact that learners must become dissatisfied with their existing conceptions, as well as find new concepts intelligible, plausible and fruitful before conceptual restructuring will occur.

Furthermore, constructivism indicates that each learner must put together ideas and structures that have personal meaning if he or she is to learn. In order words, individual actively generates their personal meanings. Edward and mercer (2010) confirmed the above by saying that learning is regarded as a social activity in which learners are engaged in constructing meaning through activities, discussions, and negotiations among peers, students and teachers. Learners' individual constructions of meaning occur when their ideas are compared explored and reinforced in social setting with each student having the opportunity to reorganize his/her ideas through talk and listening (Solomon, 2013). Through social interactions, learners become aware of others ideas, seek confirmation of their own ideas and reinforce or reject their personal constructions (Maor & Taylor, 2010).

From the foregoing, a learner is seen as the owner of his ideas and that understanding can be only be created in the learner from experiences and discussions among peers, fellow students and teachers (Stofflet, 2010) Solomon, 2015). There is therefore, the need to link the existing memory with the present experiences in classroom setting which would lead to existing memory with the present experiences in classroom setting, which would lead to reinforcing or restructuring and of course successful learning. This indicates that learning is an act of construction.

Furthermore, the constructivist views about learning suggest that “knowing” means being able to construct something. Therefore, knowledge must be attained in a personal sense and cannot be transferred from one person to another like filling vessel (Nworgu, 2014) which reduces the learners to a passive element who requires to sit down in the instructional setting, receives and add new information to his pre-existing knowledge. This indicates that knowledge can be accumulated bit by bit, subject and be available to transfer to the learner.

This is typical to traditional classroom where the teacher carriers on with old ideas and old ways of doing things (Nworgu, 2017). This technique places the learners as a passive recipient of knowledge rather than an active participant in the

construction of his or her own knowledge. Constructivist view learning more than this and sees the learner as creative, dynamic and with a free will. He is seen as the controller of his environment (Nworgu, 2014).

According to (Driver, 2011) students' prior ideas seem to intrude into classroom learning. In practical activities, students' ideas influence the observations they make, the inferences they draw and what they understand from formal learning situations. Listening to lectures as well as reading from textbooks (Vienno et al. 2010) In their independent studies noted that students' alternative conceptions may persist despite teaching except attempt is made to intervene and being about conceptual change. (Stofflect, 2017) stated that what a student learns is a result of the interaction between what he brought to the learning situation and what he experiences. Supporting this view, (Tobin 2010) reported that in a learning process, learners create perturbations which arise from attempts to give meaning to particular experiences through the imaginative use of existing knowledge. He went on to say that a resolution of these perturbations leads to an equilibrium state of the learner where new knowledge is constructed to cohere with a particular experience and prior knowledge. In effect it means that the interaction which brings about perturbations causes a restructuring of the existing conception or conceptual changes in learning process. To achieve the above purpose, different learning strategies have been proposed recently. Most of these are socio-cultural and inquiry oriented. Examples of such strategies include the use of analogy, inquiry, cooperative learning, problem solving and constructivism. (Nwosu & Nzewi, 2019). Constructivism therefore is a model of instruction and learning as an interactive process in social settings. It is problem solving oriented, allows students to explore and work in groups, making meaning of task and setting out to solve problems and that are perplexing to them.

Constructivist strategies are organized into four categories namely, invitation, exploration, proposing explanations and solution taking action, (Yager, 2010). He explained further that constructivist practices require teachers to place students in more central positions in the whole instructional programme. This means that student idea should form a basis for discussion and investigation in the classroom. Tobin (2016) agreed with the above and stated that teachers should see themselves as mediators of the learning process and they should as well as provide constraints for students to channel their thinking in productive direction. Teachers are to interact with students to a greater extent than what is obtained in traditional classroom to ascertain what students know and what they are thinking and that learning should be interactive, cooperative and collaborative. (UNESCO 2012) while recommending constructivism instructional approach to learning explained that in a constructivism learning environment, student construct their own knowledge by testing idea and approaches based on their own prior knowledge and experience. Applying these to new task, contest and situations and integrations the new knowledge gained with pre-existing intellectual constructs. UNESCO explained further that in a constructivist environment involves developing learning communities comprised of students, teachers and experts who are engaged in authentic tasks context, closely related to work done in world.

A constructivist learning environment also provides opportunities for learners to experience multiple perspectives, through discourse or debate, learner is also to see issues or problems from different points of view, to negotiate meaning, and develop shared understanding with others. The constructivist learning environment also emphasizes authentic assessment of learning environment also emphasizes authentic assessment of learning rather than the traditional paper/ pencil test.

(Knowles & Kinsey, 2015) listed eight characteristics that describe constructivist.

Learning environment as follows;

1. Constructivist learning environment provide multiple representations of reality
2. Multiple representations avoid over simplification and represent the complexity of the real world.
3. Constructivist learning environments emphasize knowledge construction knowledge reproduction
4. Constructivist learning environments emphasize authentic task in a meaningful context rather than abstract instruction out of context.
5. Constructivist learning environments emphasize authentic task in a meaningful contest rather than abstract instruction out of context.
6. Constructivist learning environments encourage thoughtful reflection on experience.
7. Constructivist learning environment enable "Context and content dependent knowledge construction"
8. Constructivist learning environment support collaborative construction of knowledge through social negotiation, not competition among learners for recognition.

In the same vein (Honebein, 2015) also noted that designers of constructivist learning environments live by seven pedagogical goals namely;

1. Provide experience with knowledge construction process
2. Students take primary responsibility for determining the topics or subtopic in a domain they pursue, the methods of how to learn and the strategic or methods for solving problem. The role of teacher is to facilitate this process.

3. Provide experience and appreciation for one correct solution. There are typically multiple way to think about and solve problems, students must engage in activities that enable them to evaluate alternative solutions to problems as a means of testing and enriching their understanding.
4. Embed learning in realistic and relevant contexts: most learning occurs in the context of school whereby educators remove the noise of real-life from learning activity or instance, world problems in mathematics text books rarely relate to the types of problems found in real life. The result is the reduced ability of the students to transfer what they learn in school to everyday life. To overcome this problem, curriculum designs must attempt to maintain the authentic context of the learning task. Educators must ground problems within the noise and complexity that surrounds them outside the classroom. Students must learn to impose order on the complexity and noise as well as solve the core problem.
5. Encourage ownership and voice in the learning process: This illustrates the students' centeredness of constructivist learning. Rather than the teacher determining what students will learn. Students play a strong role in identifying their issues and directions as well as their goals and objectives. In this frame work, the teacher as a consultant who helps students to frame their learning objectives.
6. Embed learning in social experience: intellectual development is significantly influenced through social interactions thus; learning should reflect collaboration between both teachers and students and student and students
7. Encourage the use of multiple mode of representation: Oral and written communication are the two most common forms of transmitting knowledge in educational settings. However, learning with only these forms of communication limits how students see the world. Curricular should adopt additional media, such as video, computer, photographs and sound to provide richer experience.
8. Encourage self-awareness of the knowledge construction process: A key outcome of constructivist learning in knowledge how we know. It is the students' ability to explain why and how they solved a problem in a certain way; to analyze their construction of knowledge and processes, this process is called "reflexivity" an extension of metacognitive and reflection activities.

The seven pedagogical goals of constructivism offer designers a solid framework which to build learning environments. By designing learning activities that satisfy the goals, the signer makes an effort to put theory into practice. In this way the learning environment will promote higher order thinking skills in the students. In relation to this view of constructivism, the constructivist learning process as used in this study is seen as a process of 'meaning-making' in socially situated contexts whereby students construct their own knowledge by testing ideas and approaches based on their prior knowledge and experience in auto-mechanics, applying these to new tasks, contexts and situations, and integrating the new knowledge gained with pre-existing intellectual constructs.

Conceptual framework

Conceptual Framework presents ideas, rules, or beliefs of how something is developed, is done or on which decisions are based. The concept of constructivism and constructivism instructional strategies employed in this study, including the concept of auto-mechanics in Technical Colleges are presented below:

The concept of constructivism

Constructivism according to (Thanasoulas,(2015) is a theory of learning based on the ideas that knowledge is confirmed by the knower based on mental activities. Similarly, Hoover (2016) pointed out that constructivism central idea is that human learning is constructed. Learners build new knowledge upon the foundation of previous learning. This view of learning according to Hoover sharply contracts with one in which learning is the transmission of information from one individual to another, a view in which learning is the transmission of information from one individual to another, a view in which reception, not construction is key. Supporting this view, (Kozloff,2019) noted that constructivism challenges the assumption and practice of reductionism that have pervaded our educational practices for generations. In a deficit-driven reductionism framework, effective learning takes place in a rigid, hierarchical progression. Learning then is an accumulation of isolated fact.

In construction view of learning process, (UNESCO,2013) explained that learners are active agents who engage in their own knowledge construction y integrating new information in their scheme or mental structure. The learning process is seen as a process of meaning-making' in socially, culturally, historically and probability situation context. In the view of constructivist, learning is a constructive process in which learner is building an internal illustration of knowledge, a personal interpretation of experience. Two important notions orbit around the simple idea of constructed knowledge. According to (Hoover ,2017) the first is that learners construct new understanding using what they already know. There is no tabula rasa on which new knowledge is etched. Rather, learners come to learning situation with new or modified knowledge they will construct

from new learning experiences. The second is that learner is active rather than passive, learner confront their understanding in light of what they encounter in the new learning situation. If what learners encounter is inconsistent with their current understanding, their understanding can change to accommodate new experience.

Methodology

A quasi-experimental research design was used for this study. Specifically, the pretest, post-test non-equivalent control group design was adopted for the study.

Population and sampling procedure

The population of the study consisted all the students in Tech 11 in all the technical colleges in lagos state during the 2022/2023 academic session. A sample of size of 340 students were selected from the sample using multi stage random sampling technique and in this case, 182 students constituted those in the experimental group while students totaling 158 constituted the subjects in the control group.

Instruments for data collection

The instruments used for data collection in this study were Cognitive Achievement Text (CAT). The CAT was used to test the students' cognitive achievement and retention of learning in auto-mechanics. The CAT contained multiple choice items and was developed based on the content of petrol engine maintenance work in the technical college syllabus-module CMV 11.). The items of the CAT were drawn based on table of specifications built in order to ensure the content validity of the test. The reliability coefficient of 0.80.was obtained for the CAT using pearson product moment correlational coefficient Other instruments adopted were constructivist inquiry - based lesson plans and conventional lesson plans *while face validity was used to ensure the validity of the lesson plans using three experts.*

Experimental procedure

The pretest was first conducted before the commencement of the treatment. The pretest featured the administration of the Cognitive Achievement Test (CAT). on the students in both experimental and control groups. The results obtained from the pretest provided baseline data on the dependent variable (Cognitive achievement) before treatment.

The pretest was immediately followed by the treatment. During the treatment, the experimental group was taught with constructivist inquiry -based lesson plan, while the control group was taught with conventional lesson plans. The constructivist inquiry -based lesson plan incorporated five learning strategies: thinking skill, oral discourse, active learning, collaborative learning skills and framing strategies to a greater extent emphasized students' active participation in their learning process, group learning, connectedness of the lesson to real-world situation and practical hand-on activities.

Method of data analysis

The data collected from the pretest, posttest, and retention of learning were analyzed using mean to answer the research questions. The pretest-posted mean gain of each group (Control and Experimental groups) were compared to determine the group that performed better to answer questions. The null hypotheses were tested using Analysis of Covariance (ANCOVA) at 0.05 level of significance.

Presentation of results

The results of the data analysis for the study were organized according to the research questions and hypotheses that guided the study.

Research Question One.: .What are the mean achievement scores of students taught auto-mechanics using the inquiry- based instructional strategy and those taught using the conventional lecture and demonstration teaching methods?

Table 1: Mean and Standard Division of Pre-Test Scores of Experimental and control Group in the Auto-mechanics Cognitive Achievement Test(CAT)

GROUP	N	Pre-Test		POST-TEST		MEAN GAIN
		X	SD	X	SD	
Experimental	182	3.85	1.47	35.60	1.81	31.75
Control	158	3.77	1.47	19.71	3.89	15.94

The data presented in Table 1 shows that the experimental group had a mean score of 3.85 and standard deviations of 1.47 in the pre-test with mean score of 35.60 and standard deviation of 1.47 in the pre-test and a mean score of 31.75. The control

group had a mean score of 3.77 and a standard deviation of 1.47 in the pre-test post-test gain of 15.94. With this result, the students in the experimental group performed better than the students in the control group in the cognitive achievement test.

Research Question two: What are the mean scores of students taught auto-mechanics using the inquiry-based instructional strategy and those taught using the conventional lecture and demonstration teaching methods in the test for retention of learning?

Table 2: Mean and Standard Deviation of Achievement Scores of Experimental and Control Group in Auto-mechanics Cognitive Achievement Post-Test and Test for Retention Learning

GROUP	N	Pre-Test		Test for Retention	
		X	SD	X	SD
Experimental	182	35.60	1.81	34.58	3.24
Control	158	19.71	3.89	8.62	3.58

Table 2 shows that the students in the experimental group had a post-test mean score of 35.60 with standard deviation of 1.81 and a mean score of 34.58 with standard deviation of 2.24 in the test for retention of learning, while the students in the control group had a post-test mean score of 19.71 with test for retention of learning. The results therefore indicate that students taught Auto-mechanics with the constructivist instructional approach retained their learning better than those taught with the conventional teaching methods.

Hypotheses One There is no significant difference between the mean achievement scores of students taught auto-mechanics with inquiry-based instructional approach and those taught using the conventional lecture and demonstration teaching methods.

Table 3: Summary of Analysis of Covariance (ANCOVA) for Test of Significance between the Mean Scores of Experimental and control groups in the Cognitive Achievement.

Score of Variation	Sum of Square	DF	Mean Square	F	Sig of F
Covariates	13.790	1	13.790	1.566	.212
Pre-test	13.790	1	13.790	1.566	.212
Mean Effects	21366.499	1	21366.499	2426.121	.000
Group	21366.499	1	21366.499	2426.499	.000+
Explained	21366.546	2	10683.273	1213.063	.000
Residual	2967.910	337	8.807		
Total	24334.456	339	71.783		

The data presented in Table 3 shows that the F-value for group is 2426.121 who significance of .000, which is less than 0.5. The null-hypothesis is therefore rejected at 0.05 level of significance. With this result, there is significant difference between the mean scores of students taught with constructivist instructional approach and those taught using conventional teaching method in Auto-mechanics Cognitive Achievement test.

Hypothesis two: There is no significant difference between the mean retention scores of students taught auto-mechanics with inquiry-based instructional approach and those taught using the conventional lecture and demonstration teaching methods

Table 4: Summary of Analysis of Covariance (ANCOVA) for Test of Significance between the mean scores of experimental and Control groups in the Test for Retention of learning.

Source of variation	Sum of squares	DF	Mean Sqaure	F	Sig of F
Covariates	23.924	1	23.924	2.777	.97
Pre-test	23.924	1	23.924	2.777	.097
Main Effects	57028.997	1	57028.997	6619.048	.000
Group	57031.997	1	57028.997	6619.048	.000+
Explained	57031,555	2	28515.669	3309.660	.000
Residual	29034.894	337	8.616		
Total	59934.894	339	179.799		

Significant at sig of F < 05

Table 4 shows that the F-value for group is 6619.048 with significant of at .000, which is less than .05. the null-hypothesis is therefore rejected at .05 level of significance. With this result, there is significant difference between the mean scores of students taught with constructivist instructional approach and taught using conventional teaching method in Auto-mechanics test for retention.

Discussion of findings

The data presented in Table 1 provided answer to research question one, finding revealed that students taught with constructivist instructional approach had a higher mean score than those students taught using the conventional teaching methods in Auto-mechanics cognitive achievement test. In the same vein, the analysis of covariance presented in Table 3 confirmed that the difference between the mean teaching methods was significant. The significant different is attributed to the treatment given to the experimental group. This finding indicated that the constructivist instructional approach has a positive effect on student's cognitive achievement in auto-mechanics. This implies that the constructivist instructive achievement in auto-mechanics. This implies that the constructivist instructional approach (Collaborative learning, oral discourse, thinking skill, authentic task and learning frame) is more effective than the conventional teaching method in enhancing student's cognitive achievement in Auto-mechanics. The findings that enhancing students' Constructivist instructional approach has positive effect to students' achievement is similar to the adoption of constructivist instructional approach in the in the teaching of Thailand vocational electronic students improved the students' achievement in electronics than the students taught with traditional instructional method.

The data presented in Table 2 provided answer to research question two. Finding revealed that students taught with constructivist instructional approach had a higher mean score than those taught with the conventional instructional teaching method in the test for retention of learning. The analysis of covariance of the retention test presented in Table 4 confirmed that the difference in the score of the students taught with conventional instructional approach and those taught with conventional teaching methods is significant. This showed that the constructivist instructional approach has positive effect on the students learning in auto-mechanics. This finding stemmed from the fact that constructivist instructional approach has positive effect on the student retention of learning in auto-mechanics. These findings stemmed from the fact that constructivist instructional approach enhances hands-on activists with places learning in the hands of the students. The provision of active learning environment were students can be engaged and participate activity in class discussion increase the students' ability to explore issues and articulate their own ideas. Also, the use of open ended questions by the teacher makes the students to engage in higher order thinking task such as analysis, synthesis and evaluation. These affirms (Tochomites ,2010) view that order thinking skills, improves memory and enhances transfer of learning to another situation. (Von Glaserfield,2010) was of the opinion that by teaching students understanding. He maintained that when students learn to think, they will be able to tackle problems creatively and confidently.

In any educational practices, when students work or learn in groups collaboratively using real object, each person, in order to be an effective participant, will need to think critically in order to make logical contributions. Moreover, when students learn in groups, the bright ones always help the dull ones to understand the subject matter being learnt. This affirms (Ngeow,(2010) view that collaborative learning enhances critical thinking skills and hence, cognitive achievement and retention of learning

Conclusions

This study set out to determine the effect of inquiry-based instructional approach on the achievement and retention of learning of auto-mechanic students in technical colleges. The constructivist instructional approach (Collaborative learning, oral discourse, thinking skill, authentic task and framing) used in this study greatly affected the students learning of Motor Vehicle mechanics work. This was reflected in the auto-mechanics students' cognitive and retention of learning. In other word, student learnt auto-mechanics better when they were allowed to participate actively in the classroom teaching and learning by interacting with teacher, learning environment and their colleagues and work and learn together in groups. Also, students retained their learning for a longer time they are allowed to think on possible solution to a problem while engaging in practical activities with real objects. Tools and machine work in the technical colleges, craftsmen trained will graduate from the technical colleges with knowledge psychomotor skills, strong problem solving, creative thinking, collaborative work, and independent decision making skills which will make them to be adaptable to the present and envisaged changes in the automobile industry occasioned by technological advancement.

Recommendations

Based on the findings of this study, the following recommendations are made

1. Technical college teachers should adopt the use of inquiry- based instructional strategy to teach auto-mechanics and other vocational courses to enhance better cognitive and psychomotor achievement.
2. To enhance better retention of learning, Inquiry-- based instructional strategy should be adopted for teaching in the technical colleges
3. National board for Technical Education (NBTE.) should consider review of the curriculum for motor vehicle mechanics work programme with a view of incorporating the inquiry- based instructional strategy into the teaching of auto-mechanics
4. Ministry of Education and administrators of technical education should always organize seminars and workshops to sensitize technical teachers on the use of the inquiry –based instructional strategy.

References

- Aina, O. (2011). Nigeria Technical and Vocational Education in the near future. In Federal Ministry of Education (2010). The National Master-plan for Technical and Vocational Developmental in Nigeria in the 21st Century with the Blue Print for the Decade 2010. Abuja, FME.
- Becker, K.H, & Manusaiyat, S. (2014). A Comparison of students' Achievement and Attitudes between Constructivist and Traditional Classroom Environments in Thailand Vocational Electronic Programs. Retrieved November 15, 2016.
- Doolittle, P.E & Camp, W.G (2010) constructivism: the career and technical education perspective. *Journal of vocational and technical education*, 16(1). 32-36. Retrieved March 25, 2015.
- Federal Ministry of Education (2010) Technical Vocational Education Development in Nigeria in the 21st Century with the blue-print for the Decade 2011-2022. Abuja; Federal Ministry of Education.
- Federal Republic of Nigeria (2014). National technical certificate examination (craft level) syllabus for engineering trades based on the NBTE modular curricular. Kaduna NBTE.
- Nice, K. (2010) How car computers work. Retrieved on 18/01/2013.
- Ogwo, B. A. & Oramu, R. N. (2016) Methodology in informal and non-formal technical/vocational education. Nsukka: University of Nigeria press.
- Oranu R. N (2013) Vocational and Technical Education in Nigeria. Retrieved on July 18, 2015 from July 18 2015.
- Owoso (2016), Vocational and Technical Education Methods published by Sirco baba & sons.
- Robin, S (2010) Short paper: cognitive apprenticeship. Retrieved June 20, 2016.
- Rojewski, W. J (2012) Preparing the workforce of Tomorrow: A Conceptual Framework for Career and Technical Education. *Journal of Vocational Education Research*. Retrieved March 10, 2016.
- Tochonites, O.C. (2010) Creating an effective foreign Language classroom Retrieved on 19/04/2015 from March 6, 2014.
- UNESCO, (2012) Information and communication technology in teacher education Retrieved on 19/04/2015 from March 6, 2014.
- Von Glasser field, E (2012). Radical constructivism and teaching: Prospects, XXX1 (2) 161-173.